

**TOOLS
4CAP**

TOOLS4CAP ACADEMY MODULE VIII

FROM EVIDENCE TO PRACTICE: IMPLEMENTERS' VOICES AND REAL-WORLD LESSONS

Highlights Report

Introduction

Qualitative and quantitative tools have played a central role in the design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). They help **strengthen the legitimacy of policy choices** by incorporating a range of perspectives from stakeholders who are most directly affected by CAP measures. By combining empirical evidence with expert judgement and stakeholder input, these approaches support a more grounded understanding of needs, priorities and trade-offs. They therefore contribute to **more informed decision-making and improve transparency in policymaking**, which remains a key requirement in the CAP context.

At the same time, these tools are not without limitations. Where robust data is missing, assessments often rely on expert judgement, which can introduce variability depending on who is involved and how issues are framed. Practical constraints, such as limited time and administrative capacity, may also affect the depth of engagement and the validation of results. In addition, some actors may be hesitant to rely on participatory outputs, particularly when these are not clearly linked to formal decision-making processes or when their influence on final decisions is not evident.

ORGANISER:

21 APRIL 2026

ONLINE

38 PARTICIPANTS from 16 COUNTRIES

(Public authorities, governance bodies; researchers; innovators; and other stakeholders relevant to the agricultural sector)

PRESENTATIONS AND RECORDINGS [HERE](#)

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The [Tools4CAP Academy](#), coordinated by the [European Association for Innovation in Local Development](#) (AEIDL), organised [Module VIII, “From evidence to practice: implementers’ voices and real-world lessons”](#), on 21 April 2026. The module focused on how these tools are applied, highlighting **implementation experiences, operational challenges, and lessons** relevant to the next CAP.

The session brought together 38 participants from 16 Member States and focused on the **practical application of participatory approaches through case studies, with particular attention to decision-support tools such as the IOI Matrix, Intervention Logic and the Prioritisation Tool**. These were presented through examples from case studies developed in [Germany](#), [Poland](#) and [Ireland](#).

[Tools4CAP Academy](#) aims to provide a framework for capacity building and peer – learning to develop an attractive and tailored training programme to meet the end users’ needs. [Tools4CAP](#), coordinated by ECORYS, is a project embedded in the Horizon Programme that involves 21 partner organisations from 18 EU countries with outstanding expertise in economic, environmental, climate and social issues, new data sources and monitoring technologies, as well as in stakeholder engagement, social, environmental, and animal welfare-related data and indicators, in agricultural and rural development contexts.

Conceptual and strategic framing for CAP implementation

Bérénice Dupeux

Tools4CAP project’s coordination (Ecorys)

Tools4CAP has contributed to strengthening evidence-based approaches in CAP Strategic Plans through the development, testing, and application of analytical, participatory and monitoring tools across different Member States. This work has generated insights on how such tools can support the design, implementation, and review of CAP Strategic Plans, particularly in a context where future governance decisions may provide Member States with greater flexibility in policy design.

Building on this work, the project has also developed **reflections on the next Multiannual Financial Framework, presented in the policy brief “CAP 2028–2034: Navigating change for an evidence-based policy”** (December 2025). The brief explores the proposed changes in governance structures and highlights the importance of reliable analytical tools, consistent data systems, and sufficient institutional capacity to ensure transparency and comparability across Member States.

6 key political challenges for evidence-based policymaking

1 Budgetary uncertainty

Flexible and allocated funds make multi-year planning unpredictable

2 Complexity and disincentives in co-financing arrangement

Higher national contributions may sideline agri-environment measures

3 Reduced policy design rigour

No clear common policy design requirement risk weakening intervention logic and results links

4 Degressivity and capping impacts

Highly variable effects across Member States need national IA

5 Farm stewardship ambiguity

Vague rules replace 20-year GAEC baseline – threatens level playing field

6 Analytical and admin capacity

Larger demands for fewer prescribed tools; risk of lobby-driven policy

Bérénice Dupeux (ECORYS), coordinator of Tools4CAP, presented the recommendations included in the project's policy brief, highlighting proposed **priorities for EU institutions, Member States and the research community.**

These recommendations underline the need to strengthen evidence-based policymaking through better coordination, stronger analytical capacity, and more consistent use of tools across governance levels.

EUROPEAN COMMISSION AND CO-LEGISLATORS	MEMBER STATES	RESEARCHERS
<p>Prioritise data and science; require harmonised templates for NRPP design and evaluation.</p>	<p>Establish interministerial groups; track stakeholder inputs with transparent digital tools.</p>	<p>Address budgetary data gaps and enable cross-country, cross-period comparisons.</p>
<p>Promote balanced stakeholder representation; evaluate engagement processes.</p>	<p>Ground priority-setting in evidence; use SMART indicators within clear intervention logic.</p>	<p>Apply integrated mixed-method approaches — qualitative and quantitative, multi-scale.</p>
<p>Define clear approval process to prevent renationalisation; ensure level playing field.</p>	<p>Assess degressivity and co-financing impacts by farm type and region; adjust regularly.</p>	<p>Conduct independent critical analysis of NRPPs and CAP chapters.</p>
<p>Leverage data interoperability rules and Single Gateway for researchers.</p>	<p>Safeguard regional autonomy; ensure efficiency of public spending is regularly reviewed.</p>	<p>Advocate for SMART objectives and explicit intervention logic in policy design.</p>
		<p>Contribute to standardised indicators and evaluation frameworks.</p>

How this works in practice: insights from Germany, Poland and Ireland

Turning evidence into practice requires **stronger use of qualitative methodologies and decision-support tools.** In this context, and to achieve the objectives presented before, participatory approaches can help ensure that policy decisions **remain transparent and legitimate, while also better reflecting the views of those directly involved, particularly in the next CAP programming period.** Furthermore, it was mentioned that bottom-up approaches can support more meaningful participation and encourage joint design processes, in which policies are developed collaboratively and more closely reflect the needs of those involved.

Germany Case Study (Hesse): IOI Matrix for Eco-schemes & AECM Coherence
Carla Wember (Institute for Rural Development Research (IfLS))

The German case study looked at how the Intervention–Outcomes–Impact (IOI) Matrix can be used to assess coherence between national eco-schemes under Pillar I and regional Agri-Environment-Climate Measures (AECM) under Pillar II in the federal state of Hesse.

As in other Member States with shared competences, the CAP governance in Germany involves both national and regional levels. Ensuring consistency between these instruments and among the stakeholders involved is important to avoid overlaps, gaps, or unintended inconsistencies.

Key findings

- The IOI matrix proved useful in making the **links between national and regional measures** more visible.
- It helped **clarify how different interventions interact** and supported more structured discussions on programme coherence, providing a practical basis for considering adjustments to programme design.
- The tool worked well as a **bridge between analytical work and administrative decision-making**.
- **Strong contributions of eco-schemes and HALM measures** to water protection, nutrient management, and biodiversity.

Lessons learned

- **Usefulness for strategic planning:** the tool proved highly effective to visualise complex intervention logic and facilitate transparent, structured dialogue between researchers and policymakers.
- **Cooperation with stakeholders:** it works well even in small expert groups, although wider participation would increase legitimacy.

Recommendations

- Conclusions suggest that the IOI matrix could be more systematically **integrated into the planning and review of eco-schemes and AECM**, which would require stronger data foundations and improved estimation of impacts.
- **Wider and earlier stakeholder involvement** should be considered in future applications to strengthen the quality and legitimacy of coherence assessments.

Polish Case Study: Constrained Cumulative Voting for prioritisation in CAP Strategic Plan design

Barbara Wieliczko (European Rural Development Network (ERDN))

The Polish case study examines whether Constrained Cumulative Voting (CCV) can improve the transparency, inclusiveness, and evidence base of the prioritisation of needs during the design of the CAP Strategic Plan. During the 2023–2027 programming process, limited time for open discussion meant that priorities were largely shaped by past approaches rather than by a structured assessment of needs. Against this background, the case study tested a more structured participatory method to support prioritisation, improve understanding of trade-offs in CAP

decision-making, and encourage a more open discussion on the use of tools in CSP design and implementation.

The approach in Poland was based on a workshop involving stakeholders from the quadruple helix (public administration, business, academia and civil society), and participants were asked to **distribute 100 points across a list of identified needs**, within defined upper and lower limits to avoid dominance by any single preference.

Polish case study overview and ambition

Key findings

- The cumulative voting method was found to be relatively **easy to understand and apply**. It improved transparency in the prioritisation process and helped strengthen stakeholder ownership.
- It also made it **easier to identify tensions** between different policy priorities and to document them in a structured way.
- At the same time, the results proved **sensitive to several factors**, including the choice of criteria, the rules for point allocation, the composition of participants, and the way in which needs were defined.
- More complex or multi-dimensional needs were particularly difficult to assess consistently, highlighting the **importance of working with a limited number** of clearly defined and well-structured needs.

Lessons learned

- The exercise was based on a small group of participants that did not fully represent all potential stakeholders involved in the CAP Strategic Plan elaboration. Time constraints and limited political engagement from the ministry also affected the process. In addition, there is a risk that participatory tools of this kind may be **seen as symbolic** if they are not clearly linked to actual decision-making.

Recommendations

- Final conclusions suggest that **prioritisation exercises should remain simple, transparent and inclusive** and that needs should be clearly defined, avoiding overly complex or multi-dimensional formulations.
- Criteria should be carefully designed and tested with all stakeholder groups, including the rules governing the allocation and limits of points. This could help **prevent the dominance of individual preferences**.
- For more complex policy objectives, **hybrid approaches** combining methods may be more appropriate.
- Further work should also focus on **adapting prioritisation tools to different stakeholder groups** involved in CAP Strategic Plan design.

Ireland Case Study: Developing Intervention Logic (IL) to improve CAP monitoring and evaluation

Trevor Donnellan (Teagasc)

The Irish case study responds to the need for clearer causal links between CAP interventions and key outcomes, including farm income, landscape quality and food security. The work focused on developing a detailed intervention logic to map how CAP measures are expected to translate into outputs and outcomes.

Intervention Logic is a qualitative tool or visual map that explains and visualises the overall concept of an intervention. It begins with the problem that motivates policy action through to the expected outcomes and impacts, and it describes how the intervention is expected to work, including the assumptions on which it relies.

Key findings

- The intervention logic diagram showed how Ireland's main CAP direct payment measures contribute to outcomes such as **farm income stability, income distribution, generational renewal** and **environmental sustainability**.
- It helped **clarify the expected outcomes linked to individual interventions** and supported the identification of relevant performance indicators.
- It also made it possible to highlight a set of feasible indicators, while at the same time **identifying data gaps and estimation challenges** that will need to be addressed.

Lessons learned

- Intervention logic helps **identify where policies overlap, where policy gaps may exist, and where more targeted measures may be needed** for specific groups, such as small farms, farms in disadvantaged areas, or young farmers.
- Intervention Logic can help policymakers make clearer **links between specific measures and the outcomes** they are expected to achieve.
- Intervention Logic development also highlights the **importance of involving stakeholders early** in the process, and the need for better data in areas such as risk management, competitiveness and agricultural diversity.

Recommendations

- Insights of the case study suggest that the development of intervention logic should follow a structured and evidence-based process, **starting with a literature review and followed by workshops** involving officials and subject-matter experts. A draft version should then be reviewed by relevant stakeholders before being finalised and made available for wider use.
- The intervention logic should be treated as a living document, updated over time and used actively to support monitoring, evaluation, and CAP Strategic Plan design. The process should be **guided by at least one person with experience** in policy planning and evaluation.
- The Irish experience suggests value in **extending intervention logic across all CAP Strategic Plan interventions**, while strengthening environmental and social indicators to allow for a more complete assessment of policy impacts.

Strengthening CAP Strategic Plans: lessons learned for the next programming period. Roundtable summary

The roundtable of Module VIII, moderated by **Simone Sterly** from IfLS, brought together experiences from the case studies to share reflections with the audience on key lessons learned from the application of tools supporting the design, implementation, and monitoring of CAP Strategic Plans in Germany, Ireland, and Poland. The discussion

provided a set of complementary reflections on the relevance and limitations of the participatory and decision-support tools presented within the Tools4CAP project, particularly in view of the forthcoming programming period and the evolving design of CAP under the MFF 2028-2034.

Use of cumulative voting and prioritisation mechanisms in multi-stakeholder settings

The discussion highlighted cumulative voting approaches as relevant tools to structure stakeholder prioritisation in CAP-related negotiation and planning processes, particularly in contexts marked by diverging and competing objectives. In such settings, interest groups often tend to frame their full set of priorities as equally important, or even as non-negotiable, which can make it difficult to identify real priorities and move towards balanced outcomes.

Cumulative voting was described as a mechanism that helps translate qualitative policy preferences into more explicit prioritisation structures, requiring stakeholders to rank objectives instead of simply listing them. **This was considered particularly relevant given the constraints of finite financial and administrative resources, which inevitably require trade-offs across objectives and stakeholder demands.** The approach was therefore regarded as potentially more transparent for aggregating stakeholder preferences, supporting the identification of

priority objectives that can realistically be addressed within negotiated policy outcomes. It was also seen as particularly valuable in the context of the next CAP programming period, where such trade-offs may become even more acute.

I think one of the challenges at times, when different interest groups are setting out their objectives or what they would like to see achieved, it can be very difficult to get some of them to list what their priorities are because, in some cases, these are almost like negotiating positions.

Trevor Donellan, Teagasc

Safeguarding regional specificity in CAP strategic planning processes

A second key issue concerned the representation of regional diversity within national and regional strategic planning frameworks, particularly in the context of the future National Regional Partnership Plans (NRPP).

The discussion emphasised that **evidence from previous strategic planning processes indicates that regional-level perspectives are not always sufficiently captured or explicitly reflected in aggregated national planning exercises.** This creates a structural risk that those region-specific priorities, including agricultural sectors that are particularly important in certain territories, may be

overlooked during the aggregation and prioritisation of needs.

Such imbalances may lead to uneven resource allocation, with implications for regions characterised by specific agricultural, environmental, or socio-economic conditions. To address this, it was stressed that participatory and prioritisation tools should be complemented by design features that ensure territorial representation and safeguard niche or region-specific needs.

I think that there have to be some tweaks made in this process to really ensure that these specificities, regional specificities and specific needs are still there so that we ensure a bit of money for these specific needs.

Barbara Wieliczko, ERDN

Accessibility and usability of intervention logic frameworks

The intervention logic tool was discussed as a structurally robust framework for linking objectives, outputs, and impacts, with clear analytical value in CAP-related planning and evaluation processes. However, **several limitations were identified** regarding its usability in participatory settings.

In particular, the approach may be perceived as highly **technical and academically oriented**, which can reduce accessibility for non-specialist stakeholders. The associated terminology (e.g. outputs, outcomes, impacts, indicators) could be considered difficult to interpret for

actors without experience in policy evaluation or programming. Moreover, full visual representations of intervention logics were described as **complex and potentially difficult to operationalise**, especially if introduced at early stages of participatory processes.

This raises a key design consideration for CAP participatory approaches, ensuring that planning frameworks remain understandable and usable for a broad range of stakeholders, in order to avoid exclusion effects linked to methodological complexity.

Structuring stakeholder engagement and formalising participation processes

A recurring point in the discussion was the need to **strengthen stakeholder engagement beyond ad hoc or informal consultation practices, particularly during the**

If I look at the part of fostering discussion, I actually think that the IOI matrix can be very helpful, for example, to have the possibility of co-creating objectives or prioritising objectives for the process, and then have a part where, more based on expert knowledge, the matrix is actually populated.

Carla Wember, IfLS

design phase of policy instruments. Effective participatory processes were described as requiring tools that support a structured formation of political will, rather than relying exclusively on open consultation formats.

This implies a clear differentiation between (i) deliberative spaces for discussion and articulation of stakeholder priorities, and (ii) formalised mechanisms through which inputs are systematically collected and integrated into policy design. Evidence from different focus group experiences reinforced that effective participation depends on combining interactive prioritisation processes with well-defined institutional channels for input submission and integration.

This dual configuration, linking participatory prioritisation with expert-driven specification, was considered relevant for balancing inclusiveness with analytical robustness in policy design processes.

Key messages and wrap-ups

A cross-cutting conclusion from the discussion was the central importance of **process design in participatory policy development.** A key requirement identified was strong transparency in decision-making, particularly regarding how priorities are defined, negotiated, and ultimately aggregated into policy outputs.

It was also stressed that the effectiveness of participatory tools depends on a clear definition of roles and responsibilities among stakeholders, experts, and administrative actors. In addition, the discussion

highlighted that the performance of these tools is shaped not only by their methodological design, but also by the broader institutional architecture in which they are embedded.

Finally, it was underlined that participatory approaches should not remain purely consultative but need to be effectively integrated into formal policy formulation and decision-making processes to ensure tangible policy impact.

All presentations and recordings are available at the [event page](#).

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